

Wisdom Vortex:

International Journal of Social Science and
Humanities

Bi-lingual, Open-access, Peer Reviewed, Refereed,
Quarterly Journal

e-ISSN: 3107-3808

Wisdom Vortex: International Journal of Social
Science and Humanities, Volume: 01,
Issue: 04, Jan-Mar 2026

How to cite this paper:

Kumari, S. (2026). Role of Gender on Stress and Adjustment. *Wisdom Vortex: International Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 01(04), 01-03. <https://doi.org/10.64429/wvijsh.01.04.008>

Received: 23 Oct. 2025

Accepted: 24 Nov. 2025

Published: 17 Jan. 2026

Copyright © 2025 by author(s) and Wisdom Vortex: International Journal of Social Science and Humanities.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY- 4.0).

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Role of Gender on Stress and Adjustment

Dr. Shalini Kumari ¹

ABSTRACT

Purpose of present research is to examine the impact gender on the level of stress and adjustment. The sample of the study consisted of two groups (male and female) each group is having 50 students. Students Stress Scale (SSS) and Bell's Adjustment Inventory (BAI) were used for the measurement of above variables. Research found that girls (158.24) feel more stress than boys (148.83) and also they (girls 46.31) have poor adjustment than boys (43.21).

Keywords: Stress, Adjustment, Gender, Students Stress

Stress as an internal state which can be caused by physical demands on the body (disease condition, extremes of temperature, and the like) or by environmental and social situations which are evaluated as potentially harmful, uncontrollable, or exceeding our resources for coping. Hans Selye (1936), defined stress that it as the non-specific response of the body to any demand for change. Stress is a many-faceted process that occurs in reaction to events or situations in our environment termed stressors Adjustment process is a way in which the individual attempts to deal with stress, tensions, conflicts etc., and meet his or her needs. In this process, the individual also makes efforts to maintain harmonious relationships with the environment. Adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs (Shaffer, 1961).

METHODOLOGY

Objective: To study the influence of gender of on the level of stress, adjustment.

Hypothesis: There will be no gender difference on the level of stress, and adjustment.

Method of the study: This study has been conducted on 100 high school students (50 male and 50 female) from Ranchi district of Jharkhand. The participants have been selected through random sampling method. The obtained data has been analysed by using different statistical techniques like Mean, SD and t ratio.

¹ Assistant Professor (Sr Scale), H.O.D, Department of Psychology, Mahila College, Khagaul, Patliputra University, Patna

Tools:

- **Personal Data Questionnaire:** This questionnaire was prepared by the researcher to obtain information about respondent's name, school, age, class, sex, etc.
- **Students Stress Scale (SSS):** To measure stress level of the students, student stress scale was used. This scale was developed and standardized by Akhtar (2011); this test has been developed to measure the major kind of stresses prevalent in the student's life from 13 to 18 year of age. In total 51 items, there are 41 positive and 10 negative items. The maximum score on students stress scale would be 255 and minimum 51. Two types of reliability were ascertained for the test- split-half reliability (0.78) and test-retest reliability (0.71). The scale has construct validity of 0.72.
- **Bell's Adjustment Inventory (BAI):** Bell's adjustment inventory was developed and standardized by H. M. Bell (1934) and adopted by Mohsin-Shamshad (1970). The scale consists of 124 items ranging from yes, no and ?. The odd-even reliabilities for the home, health, social and emotional areas and for the total test items have been found to be 0.826, 0.815, 0.844, 0.861 and 0.921 respectively. Validity is 0.58 to 0.89.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1

Comparison between Boys and Girls on Stress Mean Scores

Groups	N	Mean	SDs	t ratio
Boys	50	148.83	26.59	3.15**
Girls	50	158.24	26.76	

**Significant at 0.01 level

Figure-1.1

Comparison between Boys and Girls on Stress Mean Scores

The mean score of boys was 148.83 and girls was 158.24. The difference was significant at 0.01 level ($t=3.15$). This shows that girls are suffering from more stress than boys. The present result is consistent with previous research such as, Tolin and Foa (2006), Singh (2013), Manikandan & Devi (2015) and Vembar & Elamurugan (2012). They found that especially girls had more stress than boys, On the other hand, greater psychiatric morbidity for girls and women, particularly with respect to anxiety and depression, has let others to Surmise that burden of stress fall more heavily on females.

Table 1.2

Comparison between Boys and Girls on Total and Dimensions of Adjustment Mean Scores

	Boys		Girls		t-ratio
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Total Adjustment	43.21	14.62	46.31	15.38	1.99*
Home	8.07	4.71	8.36	4.84	0.55 ^{NS}
Health	6.47	4.63	7.22	4.26	1.50 ^{NS}
Social	14.60	4.70	14.86	4.73	0.49 ^{NS}
Emotional	13.26	5.07	13.63	5.85	0.65 ^{NS}

*Significant at 0.05 level, NS: Not significant

Figure-1.2

Comparison between Boys and Girls on Total and Dimensions of Adjustment Mean Scores

Mean score on adjustment scale of boys was 43.21 and girls were 46.21, Mean difference was significant at 0.05 level ($t= 1.99$). According to manual high score shows poor adjustment and low score shows good adjustment, so it shows that girls have poor adjustment than boys.

But between both groups dimension of adjustment was not found significant difference. This result is also supported by Basu (2012) and Gupta (2013).

Conclusion

In the result shows that girls have more stress than boys. In the conversation with students it revealed that girls have more social expectations, mental health stigma, body image issue and self doubt and perfectionism and safety concerns may be the reason that they feel more stress than boys. It is also shows that stress affects adjustment level, and boys have better adjustment.

References

- Akhtar, Z. (2011). *Student Stress Scale*. Bhargava Book House, Agra.
- Basu, S. (2012). Adjustment of secondary school students, *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 1(3), 430-438.
- Bell, H.M. (1934), *Manual for the Adjustment Inventory, Students Form* (for students of high school and college age). Stanford. California: Stanford University Press.
- Gupat N. (2013). A study of problems of adjustment of senior secondary school students, *Conflux Journal of Education*, 1(2), 93-94.
- Hussain, S. (1969), *Hindi Adaptation of Bell's Adjustment Inventory and Construction of Norms for College Students*. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, Patna University, Patna.
- Manikandan, K., & Devi, S. N. (2015). A study on stress among adolescents learners. *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(16), 2725-2730.
- Selye, H. (1936). *The Stress of Life*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1956. Rev. Ed.
- Shaffer, L.F. (1961). *Foundation of Psychology*, New York: John Wiley, Longfield & Welb (Eds.), p. 511
- Tolin, D.F., Foa, E.B. (2006). Sex difference in trauma and post-traumatic stress disorder: *A quantitative review of 25 years of research*. *Psychological Bulletin*, 132, 959-992.